

A real-time big data sentiment analysis for iraqi tweets using spark streaming

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ABSTRACT

The scale of data streaming in social networks, such as Twitter, is increasing exponentially. Twitter is one of the most important and suitable big data sources for machine learning research in terms of analysis, prediction, extract knowledge, and opinions. People use Twitter platform daily to express their opinion which is a fundamental fact that influence their behaviors. In recent years, the flow of Iraqi dialect has been increased, especially on the Twitter platform. Sentiment analysis for different dialects and opinion mining has become a hot topic in data science researches. In this paper, we will attempt to develop a real-time analytic model for sentiment analysis and opinion mining to Iraqi tweets using spark streaming, also create a dataset for researcher in this field. The Twitter handle Bassam AlRawi is the case study here. The new method is more suitable in the current day machine learning applications and fast online prediction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The much attention has been given to real-time data processing and big data analytics in the recent era [1, 2]. The increasing volume of information generated daily has made it necessary that organizations must devise ways of handling this information since the existing techniques are not efficient in handling such volume of data created at such a high rate [3-6]. The concept of big data does not only relate to the data volume; it also encompassed data velocity and variety[7]. Data can be either structured or unstructured; it can also be in the forms of a dumped file or in real-time streaming format with high velocity [8-10]. The recent advancements in social network websites have made sentiment analysis and opinion mining a trending research area [11-13]. Twitter is one of the social network applications which is used daily by millions of people to express their opinion. Iraqi dialect stream data has witnessed a tremendous level of growth [14-17] and social media applications remain the commonest source of this volume of stream data. Iraqi users express their opinion and attitude towards issues using different applications [18, 19]. The current opinion of Arabic users can be understood through real-time sentiment analysis of social media streams. Sentiment analysis

the Spark Core is provided via Spark Streaming, giving programmers the chance of learning the project and switching between apps which manipulate the stored data in memory, on disk, or data arriving in real-time. Spark Streaming was also developed to provide an equivalent level of throughput, fault tolerance, and scalability as Spark Core [38-43]. Stream processing at a high level is all about the incessant processing of unbounded data streams. However, it is a difficult task to do this in a consistent and fault-tolerant manner [44]. However, there have been improvements in the stream processing engines such as Spark, Heron, Kafka, Flink, and Samza over the past few years which enables the development and operation of complex stream processing apps by businesses [45, 46]. Spark revolves around the concept of a resilient distributed dataset (RDD), which is a fault-tolerant collection of elements that can be operated on in parallel. The number of data pieces in a batch depends on the rate of incoming data and on the batch interval. The concept of DStream at a high level is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. DStream RDD

3. RESILIENT DISTRIBUTED DATASET (RDD)

The concept of RDD is pretty unique in the domain of distributed data processing as they are introduced to address the problems of complexity and efficiency of both interactive and iterative data processing instances [47-50]. Spark 2.0 gives Spark users the leverage of not having to be having a direct interaction with RDD, but it is important to provide them with the robust mental model of the concept of RDD. Figure 3 showed the Spark Executor window. In brief, Spark depends on the RDD concept where both the idea of a large dataset representation in Spark and the idea for working with it are presented. As immutable, fault-tolerant, parallel data structures, RDD allows users to clearly persist intermediate results in memory, optimize data placement via partitioning, and use a set of rich operators to manipulate them [51, 52].

Figure 3. Spark executor

As showing in Figure 3 Spark Executer, so to execute jobs, Spark breaks up the processing of RDD operations into tasks, each of which is executed by an executor. Prior to execution, Spark computes the task's closure. The closure is those variables and methods which must be visible for the executor to perform its computations on the RDD (in this case for each()). This closure is serialized and sent to each executor.

4. SENTIMENT ANALYSIS (TEXT ANALYTICS)

Text analytics refers to the ways of extracting information from a text collection [45, 53]. The patterns and themes in a given dataset can be uncovered using several data processing and analysis algorithms and techniques. The major aim of this process is to make the unstructured text meaningful in order to extract the relationships and contextual meaning [54]. The analysis of peoples' political opinions on social networks is a perfect instance of sentiment analysis. The recent trend of tweets is shown in Figure 4. Similarly, the analysis of restaurants reviews on Yelp is another instance of SA [55, 56]. Sentiment analysis is typically implemented using Natural Language Processing (NLP) libraries and frameworks, such as OpenNLP and Stanford NLP.

Figure 4. The recent trends of tweets

5. PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed method is to design a fast analysis framework for gathering, processing, prediction, and visualization of Twitter data. There are many advantages of the proposed method that distinguished it from previous sentiment analysis frameworks. The proposed system breaks the challenge of analyzing hundreds of tweets that arrived the system memory per second. The framework provides a solution to the volume of data by HDFS storage of Spark. We provide parallel data gathering nodes and parallel processing nodes for scalable stream data. The challenge of managing the arrived tweets was solved by Kafka. The proposed framework is shown in Figure 5. The tweets arrive from twitter API in batches and are arranged by Kafka into data streams. The data stream is forwarded to Spark engine (Spark Streaming). The new method is based on lexicon-based algorithm using Apache Spark. The case study of the new method is Bassam Al-Rawi Tweets through the hashtag Bassam Al-Rawi on Twitter.

Before data processing through the Spark engine, Spark Streaming will convert the data into RDD form and transfer it to the system memory. The sentiment based on tweets will be categorized into positive, negative, and neutral as Figure 6. If the summations of sentiment of all the words of a tweet are positive, the event will be categorized as positive and placed in the positive bucket in HDFS. The negative sum of sentiment is placed in the negative bucket of HDFS, and the same for neutral. With this process, sentiment of the whole messages can be easily captured and processed and used eventually to derive the live dashboard for monitoring the trends as Figure 7. Apache Kafka was preferred in this study than the original Twitter

streamer in Apache Spark because of the lack of support for many options by the original streamer; hence, we strive to include support for buffering incoming stream for later processing or for when a certain condition is met. It also does not support streaming tweets in certain languages.

Figure 5. The proposed framework

Figure 6. DT of tweets

k-Means - Summary

Number of Clusters: 2
 Distance Measure: Squared Euclidean Distance
 Average Cluster Distance: 9.823
 Davies-Bouldin Index: 0.805

Figure 7. K-Means clusters of tweets

Figure 7 showing the ability of K-Means algorithm can be used to identifies unknown groups in complex and unlabeled data sets. The general parameters that used in this experiment was as follow: the number of clusters 2, the distance measure is squared Euclidean distance, the average cluster distance is 9.823, and the Davies-Bouldin index is 0.805.

6. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

The experiment of our proposed system was based on two implementations. First, we implemented the framework in Weka platform on 30% of Bassam Al-Rawi Twitter dataset. Second, we implemented the same percentage of data in the Spark platform. We also made a comparison in term of time consumption through the processing stage and ingestion stage. The real data sets collected from twitter API according to Bassam Al-Rawi Hashtag. The Qatari player of Iraqi origin, Bassam Al-Rawi, raised controversy in the social networking sites after scoring the only goal of Qatar's quarter-final team that led to the exclusion of Iraq from the Asian Cup 2019 in Emirates as Figure 8.

#####	محمد طوران	756570160769753088	-1	ar	<a href=	والله المفروض بسام الراوي ميحتفل بيهل بطريقة من كول عليه	0.0	1112015215934275592
#####	رحيم	11018611chealth	Bl109604837	ar	<a href=@health_Blogger1	اي????????اي والله كلش يقهون همة حرامات بسام الراوي راحت عليه حسنة	0.0	1111952429376028672
#####	نون الورد	7953186114555968	-1	ar	<a href-RT @al_karbalaeia:	وسخة ماكتبهلوشفته بمنشن بسام الراوي بيوم خسرا متعد بما معناه انتقوا كلامكم مع الناس	126.0	1111950868063182848
#####	سُ	709519341012828160	-1	ar	<a href=ZyDTH4GSs	صديقي لآعب الدجيل الطغري بسام هشام الراوي يقولك هارلك يا تحديه	0.0	1111788432622272512
#####	ترقيوي	820086890	-1	ar	<a href=2	أهداف بسام الراوي الصاروخية على التيبال في تصفيات كأس اسيا 2020 تحت 23 سنة	0.0	111168958893178880
#####	ReNgo	445333665	ReNgo_Sp528065625	ar	<a href=@ReNgo_Sport	بسام الراوي	0.0	1111609366569013249
#####	Jemma	110849675752740044	-1	ar	<a href-RT @Fjr8557463:	لوما من حطنا نفسي العراق ونفت اسم الوطنيةالوطن حيث نلن لا حيث نولديسار الراوي#	1.0	1111542504216805379
#####	بنين الصاكة	110287574	YounisMa461112276	ar	<a href=@YounisMahmoud10	بسام الراوي كلب ابن كلب	0.0	1111495212256378885
#####	محمود الحراة	781296056	basam_9724520825c	ar	<a href=@basam_97	منور بسام الراوي ربي يحفظك ويرعك ويسهل لك أمرك	0.0	1111313263164379136
#####	DHURGH	287299912	waassnnn285248752	ar	<a href=@waassnnn	بسام الراوي يحتفل	0.0	1111307486185820160
#####	Abdulrh	93300262942853297	-1	ar	<a href-RT @alkasschannel:	بي بعد التاهل لكاس اسيا تحت 23 سنة: سنذهب الي تايلاند من اجل اللقب وبطاقة الازميد:	6.0	1111267671440572418
#####	Bo Saeed	967465176168521728	-1	ar	<a href-RT @alkasschannel:	بي بعد التاهل لكاس اسيا تحت 23 سنة: سنذهب الي تايلاند من اجل اللقب وبطاقة الازميد:	6.0	1111242486582861824
#####	علي العويدي	108925318412675072	-1	ar	<a href-RT @galeb_vb:	بي ماعنده شرف.. باع وطنه.. واحتفل كلما احنا ..اعداء @_Momel313	2.0	1111203769562345473
#####	rayahi	761398907721089024	-1	ar	<a href-RT @galeb_vb:	بي ماعنده شرف.. باع وطنه.. واحتفل كلما احنا ..اعداء @_Momel313	2.0	1111202761956302850
#####	خالد الرميدي	100384216900479795	-1	ar	<a href-RT @Alwsl_123:	??? جوميز ??? جوفينكو ??? الهلال!.. اقوى فريقين في غرب قارة آسيا من وجهة نظري	74.0	1111199144926945280
#####	غلب المنصور	737373408	kareems320671391	ar	<a href=@kareemsayed @_	الراوي ..الي ماعنده شرف.. باع وطنه.. واحتفل كلما احنا ..اعداء ابن ا @_Momel313	2.0	1111185115655430144
#####	Ayman Sa	11083150c	kooora285735127	ar	<a href=@kooora	بن تعلية - بسام الراوي	0.0	1111168483771994118
#####	almataree	135662239	-1	ar	<a href=6dsF42loDA	https://t.co/rVUjyNOOGH بسام الراوي..رونالد كومان منتخب قطر	0.0	1111061484858011649
#####	bojasseem	965979548	-1	ar	<a href-RT @alkasschannel:	بي بعد التاهل لكاس اسيا تحت 23 سنة: سنذهب الي تايلاند من اجل اللقب وبطاقة الازميد:	6.0	1111019871129743365
#####	العربي الجديد	2399311781	-1	ar	<a href=t.co/5W5Qj1Xm1	ما وجه التبيه بين بسام الراوي ورونالد كومان يا ترى! الرابط البديل:	1.0	1111016291450519552
#####	قنوات الكاس	304982427	-1	ar	<a href=	بسام الراوي قائد منتخبنا الازميد بعد التاهل لكاس اسيا تحت 23 سنة: سنذهب الي تايلاند	6.0	1110991726133555201
#####	hussein gi	712635065990266880	-1	ar	<a href=	من فترة حكى الكك عن بسام الراوي وانو بييشه كبار منندي الصريرات الحرة بالعالم تحدياً	0.0	1110985851004174337
#####	Melina	891732312	kareems320671391	ar	<a href=@kareemsayed @YShaf	ميشن لل#عل بسام الراوي	0.0	111090680219484162

Figure 8. Sample of Iraqi tweets dataset (bassam case study)

This method ensures that all nearby points are in the same cluster. According to the results of k-means, agglomerative clustering and the other clustering method, we can claim that the accuracy of EM method is higher than others. However, the computational time is more, especially for the dataset with higher dimension. The future work to be done is to reduce the computational time of this algorithm to make it more suitable for high dimensional datasets. As well as testing it on more clustering problems and comparing its

performance with other clustering methods. In this study we implement different data clustering algorithms for online dataset (Bassam Al-Rawi dataset) acquired from twitter API. We made a comparison of this algorithms interm of accuracy and computational time. Figure 9 shows the clustering results. Figure 9 (a) and Figure 9 (b) show the clustering result accuracy and the clustering result in term of computational time of EM-clustreing, DBSCAN, mean-shift clustering, agglomerative clustering and K-means function from statistical and Machine Learning toolbox of MATLAB, respectively.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. (a) The clustering result accuracy, (b) The clustering result in term of computational time

7. CONCLUSION

Sentiment analysis is one of the most significant areas of text analysis. This study suggested a distributed approach to real-time sentiment analysis for Iraqi dialect sentiment on Twitter using a lexicon-based algorithm. This framework was proposed to gather, filter, and mine streams of data in three main phases of ingestion, processing, and visualization. All the components of the proposed framework have been tested and discussed based on Bassam Al-Rawi dataset. The significant improvement is the speed of processing tweets and implementation of some machine learning algorithms, such as DT and K-Means clustering based on lexicon algorithm in Weka compared to Spark. Another output of this framework is the presentation of a method to collect Twitter datasets for future studies in data analysis and other machine learning approaches.

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